

Additional file 6: Mann and Whitney test on the RPKM values of X and Y chromosomes throughout spermatogenesis

SB	p
X vs 3	<.0001
X vs 6	0.5
X vs 14	0.3974

PS	p
X vs 3	0.0032
X vs 6	<.0001
X vs 14	<.0001

RS	p
X vs 3	0.0643
X vs 6	<.0001
X vs 14	<.0001

SB	p
16 vs Y	0.2297
18 vs Y	0.1841

PS	p
16 vs Y	0.0188
18 vs Y	0.0162

RS	p
16 vs Y	<.0001
18 vs Y	<.0001